

You Humans

By Ramin Saadat

Today my mission on planet Earth comes to an end, and I must leave. A scouting mission, to survey every form of intelligence and reasoning in the cosmos. Our goal: to harvest every possible capacity so that we may face the coming cosmic challenges.

Two million years ago we knew that the primal ancestor of the lineage that reached you carried the talent for progress and the chance to outstrip all others; their behaviour had to be studied.

Two hundred thousand years ago an agent was dispatched to examine the biological evolution of the emerging species. Once your position was secured, a hundred thousand years ago I arrived on Earth. My specialty: biological intelligence and cultural evolution. From now on I yield my place to a specialist in non-biological intelligence and machine comprehension.

My home is not far from your Earth. In this same galaxy, near the black hole you call Gaia BH1, 1,560 light-years away by your measure.

On a cosmic scale the distance is trivial; we are wall-to-wall neighbours. Yet for you, with today's capabilities, the same short journey would take roughly thirty million years.

Meanwhile, it does not appear that you or your civilisation will still exist two hundred years from now.

Living on the outer lip of the event horizon grants our civilisation stability and an exquisitely efficient use of energy. There we can draw any quantity of power we desire, and information from tens of thousands of light-years falls into our hands. Other civilisations nearby share the same abundance of energy and independence from matter; they feel no rivalry, no tension with us. Like us they have their own histories and are busy gathering data and rehearsing probable futures. In your idiom, metaphorically, we too are caught in the phenomenon of the drive to survive, though for roughly one hundred million (Earth) years we have had no dependence on matter or genes.

To sketch the situation more clearly: mass, size, distance, quantities bound to matter, are not directly experienced in our physics. We revert to them only when we must communicate with beings like you in lower dimensions. We work solely with energy and information; when we speak of “waves” in our calculations it is only in relation to energy equations. Metaphorically, we live in an ocean of energy and data.

We still require the quantity “time” in our calculations, yet our physical grasp of time differs from yours. For us the present does not exist; the future is nothing but probabilities of occurrence. In our physics the past, when it reaches the edge of occurrence, collapses into a spectrum of possible futures. Metaphorically, the collapse of the inevitable past into the probable future is like a waterfall, ceaseless, endless, until eternity, with no way to pinpoint the exact instant or location of the probabilistic decay.

In our physics the past, until the moment of occurrence and observation, is merely a wave function: suspended probabilities that collapse with every event and shape the future, just as a waterfall reshapes itself moment by moment as it plunges. This view grants us complete freedom to select among probabilities, a power you have yet to attain.

If you ask whether civilisations superior to ours exist, the answer appears to be yes. We have no understanding of them; we only occasionally glimpse their shadows when they dip into dimensions we can perceive. It seems they have designed and built their own universe and its physical laws to suit their needs. In their computational framework, time has probably been eliminated; energy is the sole quantity. We have no contact with, no grasp of, their nature.

You can therefore understand that in such circumstances your destruction or survival is of no consequence to us or to anyone else. Beings like you are exceedingly common in the cosmos. We make no effort to save you from your crises, nor do we act to destroy you. Other external representatives who visit your planet harbour no such intent. From this perspective the notion of alien invasion to seize Earth’s resources or to enslave and exploit humans is absurd. Any civilisation capable of reaching your planet for observation is so

advanced that it has no need of you or the meagre resources of your tiny world. The idea that you and Earth are special is incompatible with reality.

For us what matters is how you confront challenges and the pattern of your reasoning and thought. If you cannot overcome your trials, it means you lacked the necessary intelligence and you will simply be removed from the list of candidates. On a cosmic scale you are nothing more than an entry number; you possess no distinction, unless in future you manage to demonstrate some form of salience.

I have told you all this so that you know where I come from and why I have spent so long among you.

It is customary for each of us, at the close of a mission on any planet, to leave behind a letter of sorts. Our commanders are not strict about it.

The agent who preceded me, occupied with Earth for a hundred thousand years, drew a design on stone and left it as his keepsake. At that time you had not yet invented writing or script; you only painted and carved on rock, so my colleague did the same.

Early in my own arrival I saw that carving, drawn far better than the humans of the era could manage. Modern archaeologists are right to puzzle over its origin and maker. In this particular case the conspiracy theorists who insist on its extraterrestrial provenance are correct.

Before every mission we are reminded that we must under no circumstances interfere in any way with the rise or fall of the civilisation on the planet under study, nor intervene in the affairs of its living creatures. The sole exception permitted is when an immediate and dangerous threat to ourselves exists and failure to neutralise it would cause serious harm to us or halt the mission. I too was forced several times to intervene directly so that the research would not be interrupted. Apart from those incidents, in the course of a hundred thousand Earth years I interfered with human affairs only once. I know I must explain that single case to my superior and answer for it.

Unlike my predecessor, who had to etch his farewell on rock cliffs, I now possess far greater means. To tell the truth, until five hundred Earth years ago I assumed I too would have to carve on stone or write on animal skins and leather. But in these final centuries your progress has been so swift that my superior, reading the reports I sent, thought I, or other extraterrestrial agents who come and go, had interfered. The evidence, however, was accurate.

You now have the internet and cloud storage; anything can be sent online. I therefore decided to use one of the one thousand three hundred names I have worn over a hundred thousand years and post an entry on the internet. I randomly chose a name I had already used twice and, under that identity, I upload this letter to you.

I say this so that when you see the letter on the internet you will not blame the individual. I posted it without his knowledge; he has no awareness or responsibility in the matter.

One further point must be clarified here: my use of words such as “unfortunately,” “astonished,” “pleased,” or any term carrying emotional weight does not mean I experience such feelings. These are words you use; I learned them from you. To convey meaning in this letter I have no choice but to employ the vocabulary of your emotions and reasoning. Bear this limitation in mind and avoid misunderstanding.

I know that by now many questions have formed in your minds, for you are curious creatures whose thoughts are perpetually occupied with inquiry. Questions such as: How did I conceal my identity among humans? Did I eat and sleep? When after sixty or eighty Earth years I should have aged and died, what happened? Rest assured that, to the extent I can without compromising the mission, I will tell you. After all, you have hosted me for a time, and it is your right to know.

When we prepare for a mission on another world we first read the reports of previous agents to understand the situation. Then our mind is overlaid onto the body of a sample specimen of the species under study. By this means we become exactly like one of them while remaining able to communicate with the centre, send reports, and receive instructions.

Yet despite all these precautions and preparations, my mission was not without difficulties; I wish to tell you some of them.

The first difficulty was adapting to life in a human body, a cramped, awkward frame, exceedingly fragile and vulnerable. It took time to grow accustomed to the body's limitations. You fall ill constantly and are almost continually beset by pain and disease throughout your short lives. At every age you suffer severe problems with digestion, teeth, peripheral senses, nerves, and brain that drastically reduce your efficiency.

You humans endure a very long childhood of ignorance, deprivation, and constraint within your families and cultures, which ends in a long old age of illness and incapacity. Between the two lies a brief youth and middle age in which you must labour hard and wear yourselves out completely. Accept that adjusting to this cycle of disability, suffering, toil, and disease was not simple.

In the early phase of my mission your average lifespan seldom exceeded thirty years, and nearly all of that time was spent in fear, hunger, and pain. In recent times the situation has changed; you now expect to live more than eighty years, and with less pain and suffering.

Accordingly I calibrated my own lifespan to the same scale and learned how to coexist, inside a frail and vulnerable human body, among thousands of pathogenic agents while pretending to suffer and ache as you do.

Another initial difficulty concerned the expression of inner states on the human face, things like joy (laughing), surprise, sorrow, and the like. My colleagues were unable to reconstruct these expressions properly on my human face; I lacked the ability to display them. Consequently the humans around me called me emotionless, blank-faced, stiff, sullen, and so forth; this defect caused me trouble until quite recently. But for some time now, with the shift in your culture and habits, the flaw no longer registers or causes concern.

Take, for example, the state you call laughter or laughing. Throughout the entire hundred thousand years you laughed, even in the harshest

conditions. My colleagues recorded in their reports that you laughed even when living in caves or in trees. When you obtained good food or won a battle you contracted the facial muscles and raised the corners of the mouth so that the teeth showed. Sometimes in that state you also emitted sounds indicating satisfaction. Later I saw that humans sometimes laughed while talking to one another. Yes, in the old days you laughed even in the direst circumstances.

But in these final years I have noticed that you no longer laugh. You have forgotten how to laugh. Although never in your history have you enjoyed so much clean water, food, warm shelter, and security, I have never seen you so sullen and blank-faced.

Today people who live in the same neighbourhood or street, or the inhabitants of an apartment block, do not even look at one another, let alone smile. Even when you see a child crossing the street holding a parent's hand you do not smile at the child. You turn your face away and pretend you did not see. You fear that even a glance might be construed as child abuse or psychological deviance. In my report I have noted that for the moment people are permitted to smile only at others' dogs and cats, because the laws on animal abuse are not yet clear on the matter.

The same situation obtains with other facial expressions, grief, fear, surprise. It seems you have decided to be stiff and expressionless, and in that state you feel safer. Thus the early defect, my inability to display emotional states on the face, no longer shows and is no longer considered a flaw.

Another difficulty in the last century of my stay concerned movement between different points on Earth.

For a hundred thousand years I could travel like any other creature to every corner of the planet and cross continents. Sometimes on the way I would encounter bands of robbers, government agents, or ordinary folk. I would ask whose great king owned this land and beneath whose shadow of the Vicegerent of God we walked. They would name the king of that territory.

I would repeat the name and say, “Long live the king,” and continue on my way.

Later sheets of paper called safe-conducts were issued so that individuals could travel in safety to different parts of one land or even to distant lands.

But about a hundred years ago, when you invented the passport, you were no longer allowed to travel wherever you wished on Earth, an opportunity available to every other living thing, to wind, clouds, and rain. I have seen nothing like it on any other planet. Obtaining a passport and facial imaging created difficulties for me that I will pass over.

Furthermore, at the start of the mission it was decided that I should inhabit the body of a human female, because the males were always busy hunting and fighting and had short lives. It seemed the female sex was kept away from wars and could gather more information from inside tribes and cultural groups. But I must confess that being a woman on your planet is extremely hard and dangerous work.

In those eras, about a hundred thousand years ago, women hunted alongside men. After the hunt they gathered fruits, roots, and edible seeds. In those same conditions they became pregnant and gave birth. I, who was not designed for reproduction or parturition, was exempt from that task.

My infertility of course created its own problems. Once I was buried alive because at that time numerous children meant greater tribal strength and more help for war, hunting, and food-gathering. A woman who could not bear children was incapable of her natural function and her presence in the tribe was not tolerated. After that incident I had to exit that body and reconstruct myself in another. It took time before people understood that a woman who did not give birth could still be useful, by caring, for instance, for others’ children.

Sometimes, because I could live many years without illness, I was recognised as the mother of the tribe and my words were heeded. But in later years other problems arose; the same long life to seventy or

eighty years led people to think I was a witch and they burned me at the stake.

After all these experiences it was decided that I should alternate between the bodies of both sexes, so that the dangers would be fewer and I could gather more experiences and information.

As for food, I must say that I have no need to eat, but to keep the mission natural I ate with others and performed metabolism like them without disturbing the functioning of the mind or the reception and transmission of information.

I also have no need for sleep, and in the hours when others slept I compiled and sent my reports. My wakefulness and alertness at night helped the tribe or the inhabitants of cave or hut; I could warn them of animals or enemies. But this too caused some to think me a sorceress and decide to kill me.

Of course if they did not kill me I myself, after several decades living among the people of one tribe, had to move on. To make my disappearance natural I would sometimes throw myself from a height, drift down a river, or become food for wild beasts.

In the beginning, owing to a cellular defect, carnivores had no interest in eating my carcass and my body did not decompose in nature. This flaw could have compromised the mission. I informed my colleagues and it was discovered that the spatial isomers (right-handed and left-handed) in the molecules differed from the cellular organisation of Earth creatures. Once the problem was corrected I could abandon my bodies with peace of mind, leaving no trace of myself or my past life.

Yes, for a hundred thousand Earth years I lived among you, in every desert, island, forest, village, and city. I went on sea voyages, traded, fought, raised children, begged, reigned, led, and did many other things.

I was with you through every rise and fall of your civilisation.

With you at the start of agriculture, metallurgy, and animal husbandry;
Witness to the invention of the wheel and the taming of beasts;

Witness to the creation and spread of languages, scripts, and writing;
Witness to all your wars, revolutions, intellectual, social, and political
movements.

Whenever someone harboured a new idea or the thought of building a
new tool, I went to see him.

I witnessed the birth of religions, ideologies, and intellectual
transformations.

Yes, I saw everything up close.

Now, looking back, all those events in the passage of your civilisation
resemble a river. Your historians know this turbulent, muddy river
well. They have written much about the coming and going of kings
and governments, the rise of religions and the evolution of beliefs,
wars and rebellions. But throughout those long millennia, beside that
roaring river, I saw people sitting calmly in their humble huts. Far
from the clamour of politicians and warlords. Remote from the greed
of the rich and the fervour of soldiers. People who with great effort
found a meagre loaf and ate it quietly with a smile. People who amid
all that uproar fell in love, loved, raised their children with tenderness,
and hoped to hold their grandchildren in their arms. If I could feel
emotion, my sole gratitude would be to those lovers sitting beside the
river, nothing more.

Some of you curious humans may ask: after all I have seen, after a
hundred thousand Earth years, can any people of any land or tribe be
judged superior, wiser, or more ignorant than others?

The answer is unequivocally no.

Do not imagine that this reply is given to avoid offending your human
sensitivities regarding race and blood, religion and creed, nationality
and homeland. No, that is not the case. When I say there is no
difference between any of you, from north to south, east to west of the
globe, I state a fact recorded in my reports.

No, truly you are all alike; not only in physiology, biology, and
morphology do you show no variation, but your cultures and habits

are exactly the same. I can therefore assure you that you are all identical, without omission or addition.

In fact, not only are you humans all alike, you closely resemble the other animals and creatures of Earth. The same drive to survive that exists in other animals, the same tricks and deceptions, the same predatory violence that has always arisen from the inherent scarcity of resources on your planet.

You sometimes pride yourselves on being the moral animal, yet all my data show that you have been the most violent creature on Earth. What made you lord over other creatures was precisely this violent and merciless nature, especially when you decided to practise violence collectively.

You have also been exceedingly cruel to one another. If in these hundred thousand years you ever observed anything called ethics toward your own kind, it was only because you had grown weak. When your teeth and claws had failed and violence was no longer possible. You call that condition peace.

Only in the last century or two do I see you occasionally showing mercy to one another, and not out of kindness, but because of technology. On the one hand you have built weapons so dangerous they could annihilate you all. On the other, in recent years, with the growth of technology, you have more food and no longer need to kill one another for it, though you invariably dodge the chance to give your surplus bread to the hungry.

Your wars today are less about stealing one another's bread and more about the stories you tell yourselves about the world and wish to impose on others.

Thus it must be said that you have never been kind, neither to other creatures nor to yourselves.

You sometimes call yourselves the ashamed animal or the creature with cheeks flushed with shame, using the metaphor that you possess moral understanding of your behaviour and can judge its consequences. You can feel shame for your cruelties and immoralities.

But that name is invalid, for you easily justify your violence and immorality. You know how to reconcile yourselves with your moral shame and carry on. Perhaps it would be better to call you the justifying animal.

You sometimes call yourselves the speaking animal, but that too is invalid. Other creatures also communicate with members of their own species, by chemicals or waves, whenever necessary.

You also always regard yourselves as more intelligent or wiser than the rest of Earth's creatures, whereas every animal has found original solutions to its problems and survival and knows well how to overcome environmental challenges. The very fact that other creatures have lived on this planet far longer and in greater numbers than you proves that they too have been intelligent and capable within the scope of their needs.

Whenever you grow proud of your own survival abilities, remember that before you the dinosaurs reigned unrivalled for 165 million years, whereas you have shown superiority for only a hundred thousand years and it is highly probable that you will destroy yourselves within the next thousand.

A hundred thousand years against 160 million, which is the more intelligent in survival and meeting challenges?

Also consider how long any one of you could survive alone in the wild. Would your child outlive the young of an insect or a mountain goat?

You may pride yourselves on your inventors, philosophers, and artists, but I have the exact count of them over a hundred thousand Earth years: precisely 11,768 individuals. The total number of thinkers, inventors, artists, in short, everyone who has left a trace or influenced human life, is that figure.

Compare it with the roughly one hundred billion humans of your kind who have lived on Earth from the beginning until now.

The ratio of your wise to the total human population is one in ten million.

With such a ratio, can you claim to be a thinking species? With this proportion, can you call yourselves wise and rational?

By any measure you choose, the ratio is not impressive.

Thus, if instead of speaking, moral, ashamed, rational, or thinking animal I must give you a name, I can only call you storytelling creatures. Animals who take their stories very seriously. Animals for whom stories matter more than bread, mate, offspring, or even their own survival.

Earlier I said that I interfered in your affairs only once, and that was the greatest mistake of my mission. An act that not only endangered my own studies but altered the fate of your species on this small planet forever.

Let me tell the story.

It was exactly 5,372 years ago, in Mesopotamia. The first villages and small human communities were taking shape. I moved among tribes that had settled in one place, wearing the guise of an old man in a long robe with a staff in hand, in a settlement called Eridu.

On the edge of the southern marshes of Sumer, the place where, in Sumerian legend, the first kingship descended from the heavens. The same region where the later civilisations of Uruk, Sumer, Babylon, and Susa would arise.

In Eridu groups of farmers and herders worked the land and tended livestock beside the river; every sign indicated that this population would gradually achieve internal cohesion, with division of labour and occupations, and would be able to institute some form of management for the distribution of food and surplus wealth, the same steps that intelligent beings on other worlds had already taken.

But a great problem existed: raiders. Raiders who attacked the villages from every direction, almost every week. The people hid their

primitive coins, jars of beer and wine, crops, even livestock, chickens, and roosters under the ground, inside walls, anywhere they could. They were forced to hide their women and children as well.

Every day marauding bands arrived, and the village lanes were always filled with roars, screams, blood, and fire.

The scale of the attacks was vast and came from all sides.

It was there and then that, in the greatest mistake of my professional life, I inflicted the greatest harm upon you. In my assessments I calculated that if the raids continued, these first coherent settlements on Earth would be destroyed and humans would be unable to develop civilisation. Therefore, when at three o'clock in the morning of Saturday, 11 August 3348 BCE, the village was simultaneously attacked from north and east, I decided to intervene.

As the assault began the people leapt from sleep and rushed to carry their children to the hiding places.

I stepped into a lane, white robe flowing, staff in hand, and stood in the middle of the path by which the raiders were entering from the east.

The raider chief was mounted; the rest were on foot with maces and swords, busy plundering.

The leader said to me:

“Who are you to stand insolently in my way? Move aside or I will sever your head from your body.”

I replied:

“Do you know that another band of raiders has entered the village from the north and is stealing the people’s goods?”

The chief said:

“Yes, I know; they take their share and we take ours.”

I said:

“Would you not prefer that all the wealth of this town, and of this entire land, belong to you alone?”

The man said nothing and looked in surprise at his companions, half-naked hulks holding torches. One of the raiders asked:

“How could such a thing be possible?”

I said:

“Why do you exhaust yourselves like this, in the middle of the night, holding torches and swords, running through lanes after chickens, roosters, and little girls instead of resting beside your wives? Apart from good food, soft beds, and beautiful women, what else do you want?”

The chief cried aloud:

“And how will all these things come to us?”

I said:

“By accepting that you are our lord, commander, and king. You will protect us, the people, from other raiders. In return, instead of wandering the desert, spilling blood, and going hungry, we will gladly give you the best houses, the best food, and the most beautiful women of this land. On one condition: that with your fighting men and the men we give you, you defend our lives and property.”

After a brief pause the chief said:

“That is a sensible proposal, but will the people of Eridu agree to this covenant?”

I turned to the villagers gathered in the darkness on the rooftops and said:

“People of Eridu, do you accept this covenant?”

They looked at one another; murmurs rose, and finally one of them said in a trembling voice:

“If we do this, will you and your men defend us from other raiders from now on?”

The raider chief dismounted, drove his sword powerfully into the ground, and said:

“Yes, I swear it.”

And his men roared:

“We swear it.”

One of the villagers called from the darkness in fear:

“Do you swear that you will live happily in the palaces we give you and interfere in nothing beyond our security and defence?”

The raiders answered as one:

“Yes, we swear it.”

At that moment the chief said:

“And who guarantees this covenant so that the people do not break their word and remain faithful to the pact?”

There I made the greatest mistake and said:

“I guarantee this covenant, I who have come from the heavens.”

And I raised my head to the sky.

The raiders all knelt and bowed their heads in respect.

The people whispered:

“Long live your name, you who have come from the heavens...”

An hour later I realised what a colossal error I had committed and left Eridu forever.

In the millennia that followed I watched how that simple pact with the raider chief altered the life of humans on Earth for all time.

Thereafter, for thousands of years, bands of raiders across the entire planet marched from one side to the other to seize rulership and kingship, believing it had been promised them from the heavens; raiders and peoples fought, and countless humans were killed.

Today when I hear talk of limiting power and government interference in economy, market, trade, and the freedoms of the people, I remember that summer midnight in Eridu and see that no one recalls

the pact. No one knows that governments and kings began as raiders who covenanted with the people to protect them.

The people of Eridu, and all other peoples on Earth, always remained faithful to their covenant, but the raiders broke their word and today, with the permission they received from the people, interfere in everything.

I do not know what shape your societies would have taken today had I not intervened that night. Perhaps, as on many other worlds, you too would have passed that stage with mutual aid and collective wisdom and solved the problem.

It might have taken far longer to reach that level, but had it happened, your conversations and troubles today would not revolve around raiders and the limits of their authority.

Perhaps instead of raiders your affairs would be in the hands of your best, who had assumed leadership.

Perhaps you would not have to spend your time, energy, wealth, and lives in fear of nuclear war, global warming, and pollution.

Perhaps there would be no censorship, no government meddling and encroachment in the economy.

Perhaps there would be no war, no corruption of raiders seated on thrones of power.

Perhaps today you would be discussing better free health and education services; improved care for the disabled; the joyful growth of children; the nurturing of talents; or even space voyages to distant parts of your galaxy, things that would be better for you.

Had I not been there, perhaps you would be happier and freer today.

I forced you to make a pact with raiders. Forgive me.

Yet despite everything, I must remind you of one more thing. In these final centuries you have truly progressed well. Remember that until

four hundred years ago you still believed all the stars revolved around your little Earth and considered yourselves the centre of the universe. But in this short span you have built satellites and today possess telescopes, however imperfect and primitive, with which you view the cosmos.

You have sent a spacecraft into interstellar space that so far is less than 24 light-hours from your Earth, a great achievement. Though that distance, compared with the 46 billion light-years of the observable universe's radius, is deeply discouraging, at least you have begun the effort to understand the cosmos.

You will understand that I cannot say more in this letter about the flaws in your knowledge of the universe and the nature of reality. Given what we know of you, doing so would cause unintended change in the path of your thought and reasoning and disrupt the natural flow of the mission. Especially since I myself am not a mission agent of good repute, neither for you Earthlings nor among my own kind.

Knowing that these days you have neither time nor patience to read any text, especially a long one, I must end my letter. But before parting, know this:

Your civilisation is still very young and has a long road ahead to establish its existence in the cosmos. Many civilisations like yours that I have seen on other worlds have perished at various stages for diverse reasons, sometimes even by the impact of a celestial body. Rest assured, however, that no one from outside will attack you. You and your small planet possess no feature or attraction for others and arouse no envy.

What is most dangerous for you is what you know well: yourselves, through war or by wrecking the biosphere of your tiny world.

Still, do not despair. You are astonishing creatures; at least twice before you have come to the brink of extinction and your numbers fell to a few thousand, yet you endured and persist. Perhaps you can do it again.

The next two hundred years will be decisive for you, but if survival is your aim, know that the probability is approximately 18 percent, and I see no reason it should rise.

As the Persian saying has it:

“...I depart, and I know not what your state will be, for here there is no sign of good...”

From this perspective the mission of the one who comes after me to Earth will probably be very short.

I hope one day to meet the most awake among you on a distant planet. I will have much to tell him. Finally, if I may offer you one piece of advice, it is this:

Remember, you humans are on a speck of rock, adrift in the infinite cosmos, in absolute darkness, hurtling at two million kilometres per hour. No one knows where you are going. No one will help you. You are utterly alone in your fate and have no ally or aid. Therefore be kind to one another.

And the first thing you can do for yourselves is at least to stop killing one another!

Yours faithfully,
The Old Man in the Robe